

A FUZZY BASED INTELLIGENT IRRIGATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an intelligent automated irrigation system based on fuzzy logic that measures the soil moisture content in percentage. This system employs a fuzzy controller that is implemented as a simple reflex distributed autonomous agent, thereby eliminating the cost of network connectivity and remote control of irrigation. Data logged and analyzed clearly indicated 100% moisture representing excessive moisture presence in soil, while any value below 68% was considered below average and the plant need to be irrigated. Knowing this value, the system which comprises an embedded microcontroller, soil moisture sensor and solenoid valve, was designed to automatically sprinkle water on plant when the values fall below 70%. Analysis showed that an automated irrigation system utilizing a fuzzy controller is a more efficient alternative solution to effective irrigation system. The analysis further showed that the designed model has the ability to ascertain when irrigation is needed for plant as well as irrigating plants to appropriate level.

Keyword: *Fuzzy logic, Microcontroller, simple reflex, irrigation system, soil moisture sensor*

1.0 Introduction

Plant irrigation is widely known to be an important factor in plant overall productivity. Remarkable efforts such as automating irrigation in green house farming (Kia et al., 2009), grain crops (Obota and Inyama, 2013) and Christmas tree growth (Nzokou et al., 2010). Numerous design techniques have also been employed in the design of an automated irrigation system, amongst which include the use of wireless sensor network technology such as zigbee in conjunction with a centralized control system for irrigation in farms (Gao et al., 2014; Xiang, 2011). The inclusion of fuzzy logic has not been left out of being a viable solution in control and automation theory as seen in (Gao et al., 2014; Xiang, 2011; Ed-dahhak et al, 2013). These advances have served in the efficient use of water in farm and sufficient use of water to crops for improving overall crop yield. None of these solutions are economically feasible because of the cost associated with the use of wireless communication capability, which requires more resource to learn, install and operate. The cost associated with soil moisture content quantification technique is also another barrier.

Plant overall productivity is significantly influenced by sufficient or poor irrigation. When irrigation is manually done as observed in most parts of the developing countries, it is more labour intensive, expensive, inaccurate and time consuming. Hence, it has prompted researchers into the development of automated irrigation systems for several years now (Kia et al, 2009). These researchers mostly focused on proper water resource management, timely plant irrigation and accurate soil moisture content quantification. Of these three, accurate determination of soil water content is most important to ascertain the need for plant irrigation as at when needed and

irrigating plants to appropriate level. There underlies the complexity on such a control system that not only measures accurately but also controls the irrigation plants when due. Thus, fuzzy logic as a theory proven suitable for control system design, is undoubtedly necessary to achieve an automated system with such high accuracy and efficiency (Poyen et al, 2014)

This research paper focuses on the development of a simple reflex artificially intelligent automated irrigation system that integrates fuzzy logic for quantization of soil moisture content in percentage. This system helps to ascertain when to irrigate plants, in the form of a distributed autonomous agent, eliminating the need for network connectivity and remote operation of irrigation. The system was designed with easy to acquire off-the-shelf low cost component. Thus, it makes the proposed solution to be a cost effective solution for adoption as a commercial product by farmers.

2.0 Related works

Efforts toward automating irrigation can be classified into plant specific irrigation, framing technique and technological sophistication. All are aimed at reducing the water wastage and improving crops yield.

Automated irrigation for specific plants' growth was designed for specifically irrigating some plants and not for all plants usage (Obota and Inyama, 2013). They developed an automated irrigation system that is based on monitored control and wireless sensing communication technology to improve the overall grain crop productivity. Nzokou et al. (2010) designed and implemented a tension-meter based automated irrigation system for Christmas tree growth in the United States because the area where it is widely grown lacks effective irrigation system. In addition, Krishna et al. (2006) developed an automated irrigation system for potted plants that efficiently enhance water resource utilisation. Unfortunately most of these systems were not scalable in application to other types of plants.

Furthermore, in the aspect of farming technique and technological sophistication, Kia et al (2009) developed an intelligent automated irrigation system for greenhouse that uses fuzzy logic. Xiang (2011) developed an automated irrigation system that employs both zigbee wireless sensor network and fuzzy logic controller. It uses three parameters from soil, amongst which includes soil moisture, temperature and light intensity to determine the soil moisture content. Gao et al. (2014) developed an automated irrigation system based on fuzzy controller logic and wireless sensor network. The technology is such that the interconnecting nodes are monitored from a centralized control system. Seeing the importance of cost effective automated irrigation system solution, Avatade and Dhanure (2015) developed an automated irrigation system that determines the soil moisture content using the temperature and soil moisture sensor parameters and plans the availability of water using the water level sensor in the storage. In addition, Ed-dahhak et al. (2013) developed a laboratory view of personal computer based monitoring irrigation system that uses a fuzzy controller to accurately and timely irrigate plants in green house. It employed two parameters which are the greenhouse temperature and the soil moisture obtained with temperature and soil moisture sensor respectively. Vellidis et al., (2008) utilized a grid of sensors

connected in a star topology to obtain the soil water content and temperature in cotton plants across varying soil type continuously.

2.1 System Irrigation Model

Figure1 shows the logical architecture of the proposed fuzzy based automated irrigation model. The fuzzy model designed for irrigation here is a sugeno type model, with andMethod as product, orMethod as probor, defuzzyfication method is wtaver, impMethod is prod, and aggregation method is sum. It has one input variable consisting of four membership functions; each corresponds to the soil sensor values in subgroups. Also included are two output variables corresponding to the soil moisture status, and the irrigation water sprinkler status. The soil moisture content status output variable consists of four membership function, while the irrigation water sprinkler status consists of just two membership function which corresponds to activate and deactivation of the sprinkler. The relationship between each input, leading to an output is a mapping of each input to their corresponding output through a set of four fuzzy inference rules.

Figure 1: Fuzzy sugeno automated irrigation model.

2.1.1 Input Variable and Membership Function

The fuzzy based automated irrigation system model consists of one input variable which is the soil moisture sensor in hardware/software implementation. The input variable further consist of four membership functions, which are dry, below averagely moisturized, averagely moisturized, excessively moisturized soil as shown in Figure 2. These are fuzzy linguistics describing the soil moisture content and fuzzifies the soil sensor numerical digital data into the fuzzy linguistics that the system can further process. All the input membership functions are based on the triangular membership (MF) which is specified by the three parameters {a,b,c}, for each membership function x denoted mathematically as

$$\text{Triangular}(x:a,b,c) = \max\left(\min\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}, \frac{c-x}{c-b}\right), 0\right) \quad [1]$$

Where parameters a,b,c determine the x coordinates of the three corners of the underlying triangular membership function

Figure 2: Input variable and input variable membership function

2.1.2 Outputs Membership Functions

There are two output Variables in the fuzzy based automated intelligent irrigation sugeno model in figure 1; the soil sensor status and the irrigation water sprinkler status. The soil moisture content output variable consists of four membership functions indicating either dry, below average, average, excessive moisture content as shown in figure 3. The irrigation water sprinkler status output variable consists of two membership functions, which indicates its status as either ON/OFF.

2.1.3 Soil Moisture Content Output Variable and Membership Function

The soil moisture content output variable expresses the soil moisture content in percentage and determines if the soil is classed as dry soil, below average, average, and excessive moisturized soil. This is important to help the irrigation water sprinkler output variable determine its next status (that is, the choice of membership function)

Figure 3: Soil moisture content output variable and membership function

2.1.4 Water Sprinkler Output Variable and Membership Function

Figure 4 shows the water sprinkler output variable membership function that determines the release of irrigation water to farm section or not, through a lookup on the soil moisture output variable current membership function. The two membership functions are irrigating farm and stop irrigation. A stop irrigation membership function takes effects from the moment the soil

moisture content output variable membership function becomes either excessive or average, while dry or below average triggers irrigate farm section membership function

Figure 4: Irrigation water sprinkler output variable membership function

2.2 RULE VIEWER

The rules for the fuzzy based automated irrigation sugeno model in figure 1 are detailed in Table1. These rules are formed by considering three parameters; soil sensor input variable membership functions, corresponding soil moisture content output membership functions and irrigation water sprinkler output membership functions using the fuzzy IF...THEN...AND technique.

Table1: Fuzzy based automated irrigation system rule base

RULES NO	PREMISE	CONSEQUENCE	
1	IF soil sensor =dry soil	THEN moisture content = 0%	AND irrigation water sprinkler = irrigate farm
2	IF soil sensor =below average	THEN moisture content = 45%	AND irrigation water sprinkler = irrigate farm
3	IF soil sensor =average	THEN moisture content = 75%	AND irrigation water sprinkler = stop irrigation
4	IF soil sensor =excessive	THEN moisture content = 100%	AND irrigation water sprinkler = irrigate farm

Figure 5 is the rule viewer from Mat lab, indicating a numerical input value 837 from soil sensor input variable which is further translated into 75% soil water moisture content, corresponding to average moisture content, and the corresponding irrigation water sprinkler status equals zero(0), indicating that the irrigation water sprinkler is turned off.

Figure 5: rule viewer of the fuzzy based automated intelligent irrigation system model.

2.3 Architecture of the Proposed System

The hardware architecture of the proposed system is shown in figure 6. It consists of very few off the shelf components that are less expensive and easy to acquire. These components enhanced the commercial viability of this system. The proposed system basically consists of an Atmel microcontroller, electronic soil sensor module, a cross section of water distribution pipelines from source to all sections of farm land and electronic solenoid water flow valve. Each of these components play a specialized role individually, but collectively as a system achieves the overall objective of timely and effectively irrigating the farm as at when needed.

Figure 6: Hardware architecture of proposed system

The Microcontroller is the heart of the system, connecting, controlling and supplying current to all other components. The fuzzy controller logic is coded as a firmware into the microcontroller that interfaces with other peripherals in contact with the soil and water flow channel. Without the microcontroller, the system will lack intelligent capability, despite the interaction between the soil moisture sensor and the soil. The choice of atmel328 microcontroller was most informed by its ease of programming, high processing ability (16-bit), cost effectiveness and availability. Also, its operational current and voltage requirement which is just 5v and few miliampers makes it a more suitable component for an energy efficient solution.

The Soil Moisture Sensor module is a 3.3v /2ma energy efficient soil sensor module, calibrated with resistive value from zero (0) to one thousand (1000). It serves as input device to the system, constantly monitoring the soil moisture content in a digitized form. The digital values are fed directly to the microcontroller for further processing.

The Electronic Solenoid water flow valve is responsible for controlling the irrigation of farm segment. This is determined by its state that is directly proportional to the output signal from the microcontroller, which is further directly related to soil sensor input data. The solenoid electric water flow valve consists of two states which are either ON/OFF.

The Power Supply is a 5v 2a battery and solar recharge circuitry, designed specifically for proposed system to function as an independent non-networked intelligent automated irrigation system agent. This expunges communication cost (hardware, extra power and bandwidth

utilization). Through this noninvasive power supply technique, the system is sure of uninterrupted power supply.

3.0 Results

Figure 8a shows the fuzzy system evaluation output using test data from the embedded hardware/software implementation for 4000seconds. It clearly indicates dry soil with 0% soil moisture content. In addition to figure 8b, which indicates the status of the irrigation water sprinkler as activated with a constant value of 0.5 which can be approximately equal to 1, which corresponds to irrigation water sprinkler “ON”. Therefore the system status under this condition indicates that the farm section is currently irrigated.

Figure 8a: soil moisture content (dry soil analysis)

Figure 8b: irrigation water sprinkler status (dry soil analysis)

Figure 9a shows the fuzzy system evaluation output using test data obtained from the embedded hardware/software implementation for 4000seconds. It clearly indicates soil moisture content below average corresponding to approximately 45% soil moisture content. In addition is figure 9b, which indicates the status of the irrigation water sprinkler as activated with a constant value of 0.5 which can be approximately equal to 1, corresponding to irrigation water sprinkler status “ON”. Therefore the system status under this condition indicates that the farm section is currently irrigated.

Figure 9a: soil moisture content for below averagely moisturized soil

Figure 9b: Irrigation water sprinkler status

Figure 10a shows the fuzzy based automated intelligent irrigation system evaluation output using test data from the embedded hardware/software implementation for 4000seconds. It clearly indicates average soil moisture content exactly 75% soil moisture content. Although, there are times where the soil moisture content is below average as indicate by the half shaded lines, the line did not start from the graph y-axis start point. This situation clearly supports the intelligent of the system capability to continuously monitor the soil moisture content and irrigate when needed. In addition is Figure 10b, which indicates the status of the irrigation water sprinkler mostly deactivated with values less than 0.5 or approximately 1, it corresponds to irrigation sprinkler status “OFF”. While in other times, although few, the irrigation sprinkler status appears to be “ON” with 0.5 values approximated to 1.

Hence it can further be inferred from this section that proper plant growth, though complicated and sensitive, require extreme intelligence to sustain. Therefore, the system status under this condition indicates that the farm section is both irrigated and not irrigated, with respect to time.

Figure 10a: soil moisture content for below averagely moisturized soil

Figure 10b: Irrigation water sprinkler status

Figure 11a shows the fuzzy system evaluation output using test obtained data from the embedded hardware/software implementation for 4000seconds. It clearly indicates excessive soil moisture content, with 100% soil moisture content. In addition is figure 11b, which indicates the status of the irrigation water sprinkler as activated with a constant value of 0, which corresponds to irrigation water sprinkler status “OFF”. Therefore the system status under this condition indicates that the farm section is currently irrigated.

Figure 11a: soil moisture content for below averagely moisturized soil

Figure 11b: Irrigation water sprinkler status

3.2 Discussion

The proposed fuzzy based automated irrigation system has the capability to monitor soil moisture content at the root level continuously and controls irrigation as per preset values of soil moisture content estimated in percentage, in an autonomous mode independent of other agents. The system feasibility was first proven by the fuzzy model designed, and further supported by the embedded hardware/software solution that was implemented. Also, the evaluation of the fuzzy model using data logged from the embedded system implementation further proves consistency between the fuzzy model designed and the embedded system implementation. The result from the system evaluation for soil moisture content 0%, 45%, 75%, 100% as presented in figures 8a, 9a, 10a and 11a clearly showed the efficiency and accuracy of the system in detecting and quantifying the soil moisture content. In addition, the irrigation water sprinkler status as presented in figures 8b, 9b, 10b and 11b further proves the system intelligent capability in determining when to irrigate farm section and when not to.

4.0 Conclusion

The ability to irrigate farm as a dry soil clearly indicates that the advantage of this proposed system goes beyond the obvious increase in crop yield with guaranteed sustenance of soil moisture for better plant growth. The proposed system has other advantages like time saving on the part of farmers and reduced manpower requirement. In addition to the low power requirement of the system, the proposed system can be easily met through a 9V storage battery in float with a solar panel, making the system implementation feasibility a more practicable commercial venture.

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